

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PLANNED TEACHING PROGRAMMED ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING IRON DEFICIENCY ANAEMIA AMONG ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

Iron deficiency is the most prevalent single deficiency state on a worldwide basis. It is important economically because it diminishes the capability of individuals who are affected to perform physical labour, and it diminishes both growth and learning in children. In healthy people, the body concentration of iron (approximately 60 parts per million [ppm]) is regulated carefully by absorptive cells in the proximal small intestine, which alter iron absorption to match body losses of iron.

Anaemia has well known adverse effects on physical and cognitive performance of individual's i.e. maternal and foetal health. Poor nutritional status and anaemia in pregnancy have consequences that extend over generations

Key;-Anemia

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency anemia occurs when the dietary intake or absorption of iron is insufficient, and haemoglobin, which contains iron, cannot be formed. In the United States, 20% of all women of childbearing age have iron deficiency anemia, compared with only 2% of adult men. The principal cause of iron deficiency anaemia in premenopausal women is blood lost during menses. Iron deficiency anemia can be caused by parasitic infections, such as hookworms. Intestinal bleeding caused by hookworms can lead to faecal blood loss and haem/iron deficiency. Chronic inflammation caused by parasitic infections contributes to anemia during pregnancy in most developing countries

In India, prevalence of anemia is high because of low dietary intake, poor iron and folic acid intake and poor bioavailability of iron in phytate fibre rich Indian diet. Anemia due to deficiency of other micronutrients like copper, zinc, pyridoxine and vitamin B12 are rare in India. Studies conducted by ICMR and NNMB show that prevalence of

anemia is high (50-90%) in pregnant women and 50-70% in children

. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:-

A study to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programmed on knowledge regarding iron deficiency anemia among adults in selected P.H.C at Barwala Panchkula (Haryana)

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the level of knowledge regarding iron deficiency anemia among adults.
2. To determine effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding iron deficiency anemia among adults.
3. To find out association between post-test level of knowledge of adults regarding iron deficiency anemia with selected demographic variables.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND APPROACH

Non experimental Descriptive research design with cross section survey approach was used

SETTING OF STUDY

The study was conducted at Rural community Barwala under Primary Health centre (PHC) district Panchkula Haryana.

POPULATION

The populations for the study were all the adults those who are residing in Barwala community District Panchkula Haryana.

SAMPLING

Research Design and Approach

Research design and approach → Descriptive study

Research setting → selected community at Barwala community

Collection of data → Questionnaire

Analysis and Interpretation → Descriptive and inferential statistics

- **Sample size:** The sample size was 50 geriatric people in selected community Barwala District Panchkula Haryana
- **Sample technique :** The Convenient sampling techniques were used for data collection

Aspect wise pre-test post-test mean knowledge on I.D.A

Area	Pre test		Post test		Paired t test	DF	P value Inference
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Introduction	2.0200	0.74203	2.4400	0.64397	5.957	49	0.000*
Definition ,Meaning and Causes	2.7600	1.04119	3.2400	0.89351	6.725	49	0.000*
Sign and Symptoms	0.8200	0.62890	1.1000	0.67763	2.949	49	0.005*
Diagnosis	0.3400	0.47852	0.6000	0.49487	2.648	49	0.011*
Treatment	1.1000	0.78895	1.9600	0.75485	5.087	49	0.000*
Dietary Management	3.2600	1.78211	4.6600	1.45139	4.715	49	0.000*
Prevention	1.1800	1.04374	1.8000	0.78246	3.436	49	0.001*
Complication	1.2200	0.78999	1.5800	0.67279	2.641	49	0.011*
Overall Knowledge	12.7000	3.33350	17.3800	3.98922	8.616	49	0.000*

Frequency Pre-test and Post-test knowledge level of Respondents on iron deficiency anemia

Evaluation of effectiveness of the PTP regarding Iron deficiency anaemia

Knowledge Assessment	Mean	Difference of mean	S.D.	d f	Paired t-Test	P value
Pre test	12.70	4.68	3.333	49	8.616	<0.05
Post test	17.380		3.989			

Association between Post Test Knowledge with age, sex, type of family religion, educational status and occupation

Demographic variable		Overall Knowledge						Chi square
		Inadequate		Moderate		Adequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Age in years	20-25	4	33.3	6	17.1	3	100.0	13.412 *

status and occupation

	26-30	5	41.7	9	25.7	0	0.0	DF=6
	31-35	3	25.0	15	42.9	0	0.0	
	36-40	0	0.0	5	14.2	0	0.0	
Sex	Male	3	25.0	21	60.0	3	100.0	7.126*
	Female	9	75.0	14	40.0	0	0.0	DF=2
Type Of Family	Nuclear	5	41.7	21	60.0	1	33.3	8.815 ^{NS}
	Joint	6	50.0	7	20.0	0	0.0	DF=4
	Extended	1	8.3	7	20.0	2	66.7	
Religion	Hindu	5	41.7	17	48.6	2	66.7	1.838 ^{NS}
	Christian	0	0.0	2	5.7	0	0.0	DF=6
	Muslim	6	50.0	13	37.1	1	33.3	
	Others	1	8.3	3	8.6	0	0.0	
Education Status	Illiterate	8	66.7	13	37.1	1	33.3	12.482 ^{NS}
	Primary education	3	25.0	9	25.7	1	33.3	DF=8
	High school education	1	8.3	6	17.1	0	0.0	
	PUC	0	0.0	6	17.1	0	0.0	
	Graduation and above	0	0.0	1	2.9	1	33.3	
Occupation	Employed	2	16.6	19	54.2	3	100	8.524*
	Unemployed	10	83.3	16	45.7	0	00	DF=2

Association between Post Test Knowledge with Income of the Family, Type of Diet, Consume Non Vegetarian, Practice of Preparing

Demographic variable		Overall Knowledge						Chi square
		Inadequate		Moderate		Adequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Income Of The Family	Less than 5000	6	50.0	14	40.0	0	0.0	39.76*
	5001-10000	4	33.3	10	28.6	0	0.0	DF=6

	10001-15000	1	8.3	11	31.4	3	100.0	
	15001 & above	1	8.3	3	8.6	0	0.0	
Type Of Diet	Vegetarian	5	41.7	16	45.7	1	33.3	2.613 ^{NS}
	Non vegetarian	4	33.3	9	25.7	0	0.0	DF=4
	Mixed	3	25.0	10	28.6	2	66.7	
Consume Non Vegetarian Food	Daily	2	16.7	2	5.7	1	33.3	4.690 ^{NS}
	Weekly	3	25.0	10	28.6	1	33.3	DF=6
	Monthly	1	8.3	8	22.9	0	0.0	
	Not consumed	6	50.0	15	42.9	1	33.3	
Practice Of Preparing Coffee	Sugar	10	83.3	29	82.9	2	66.7	0.510 ^{NS}
	Jaggery	2	16.7	6	17.1	1	33.3	DF=2

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the findings of the study the following conclusions were made

- Majority 68% of adults had inadequate knowledge towards iron deficiency anaemia in pre-test.
- In post-test 70% of adults enhance knowledge after P.T.P.
- The study disclosed that there was a significant association found between the level of knowledge of adults with the demographic variables such as age, sex, occupation, income of the family.

IMPLICATION OF STUDY

1. The community health nurse should play an important role. They can plan teaching on the aspect of iron deficiency anemia. Different A.V. AIDS can be used in

imparting knowledge. By applying proper nursing practice can be prevent iron deficiency anemia and save the life of human being

.2. The nursing personnel should be given inservice education to update their knowledge and abilities to identify the learning needs.

.3. Motivational counseling of the community people should be provided.

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

A similar study can be undertaken with a large sample to generalize the findings
A similar study can be undertaken with a control group.

A Comparative study can be done both in rural and urban adults.

A similar study can be done those who are suffering with iron deficiency anaemia.

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